

**D5.1. Best available multi-actor Communication and Dissemination
techniques to be integrated into EUREKA**

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

TASK 5.1 - Reinforcing the multi-actor community and identifying 'best' communication and dissemination resources to leverage in EUREKA

History of Changes

Date	Changes
05.07.2022	Dissemination level changed to public
11.08.2022	Methodology explained in more details. Illustration added to section 4

Summary

This report presents a shortlist of best communication and dissemination (C&D) tools and techniques that help multi-actor projects achieve a high impact. Task 5.1 aims to apply the lessons learned in the multi-actor project community and to maximise the impact of the C&D activities in the EUREKA project, including the 'EU FarmBook' as a two-way market platform, to serve both project partners and end-users.

This report presents the C&D channels and approaches identified as being the most effective for reaching the target audience(s) of multi-actor projects.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
C&D	Communication and dissemination
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
D1.6	Deliverable 1.6 “Report on Do’s and Don’ts for Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation and Best Practice”
DEP	Dissemination & Exploitation Plan
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
EU FarmBook	A single open source e-platform for collecting and sharing the many different types of end-user material produced by Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects.
KIP	Knowledge Innovation Panel (of EUREKA)
MAA	Multi-actor approach
MAP	Multi-actor project
T1.4	Task 1.4 of EUREKA (<i>Reviewing the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities of multi-actor projects</i>)
T5.1	Task 5.1 of EUREKA (<i>Reinforcing the multi-actor community and identifying ‘best’ communication and dissemination resources to leverage in EUREKA</i>)
T5.2	Task 5.2 of EUREKA (<i>Development of the EUREKA Communication Plan and co-ordination of communication activities</i>)
T5.3	Task 5.3 of EUREKA (<i>Finalise the EUREKA Dissemination & Exploitation Plan</i>)
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The EUREKA project has the ambitious aim to make a significant and meaningful contribution to ensure the longevity and better sharing of the research and innovation outputs of Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects, thereby contributing to the strengthening of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) in the EU Member States.

EUREKA is a multi-actor project (MAP) and, as for all other projects of this nature, its near-term success and lasting impact depend (respectively) upon two key factors:

- Relevant actors and other interested stakeholders being aware of, informed about and (where appropriate) engaged with the project throughout its lifetime.
- The outputs of the project being tailored to the needs of potential end-users, and then delivered in an appropriate, accessible and easy-to-use format.

In line with European Commission (EC) guidance on H2020 projects, it is understood there is a difference between the general function of **communication** for the purpose of raising awareness about and encouraging interaction with project activities, versus the more specific functions of:

- **dissemination** (*distributing and sharing with potential end users and interested stakeholders*)
- **exploitation** (*using for practical or policy purposes*) of the project outputs

In the interests of effective project management, these functions have been clearly separated in WP5 of the EUREKA project by: i) a broad Communication Plan developed and implemented in Task 5.2, and ii) a more targeted Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) developed in Task 5.3.

Dissemination and exploitation (D&E) are especially important in EUREKA because the project is developing and piloting a new 'tool' – the open-source knowledge reservoir (known as the 'EU FarmBook') – on behalf of the European Commission, that is planned to be taken over and developed further by a significantly larger follow-up project¹ financed under the 2021-2027 Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. Lastly, because **national and local actors** play a decisive role in D&E of EU Research and Innovation programme outputs, EUREKA communication and dissemination activities targeting these actors must be emphasised.

1.2. Objective

In accordance with the description of Work Package 5 in the EUREKA Grant Agreement, it was anticipated that Task 5.1 (*Reinforcing the multi-actor community and identifying 'best' communication and dissemination resources to leverage in EUREKA*) would enrich Tasks 5.2 and 5.3 with insights from the review of multi-actor projects in Work Package 1. In particular, it was planned that the lessons learned

¹ HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-22: Supporting knowledge exchange between all AKIS actors in the Member States by means of an EU-wide interactive knowledge reservoir (estimated budget of EUR 15 million for 7 years)

from Task 1.4 (*Review of communication, dissemination & exploitation activities by multi-actor projects*) would be of relevance to the piloting of the 'EU FarmBook' in terms of:

- Optimising engagement with the community of H2020 multi-actor projects and encouraging as many as possible to contribute with content (project results) to the online 'EU FarmBook' platform
- Helping to tailor promotion of the 'EU FarmBook' more precisely to the communication needs / habits of potential end-users (farmers, foresters, advisers etc.)
- More generally, delivering high impact information / training materials to both multi-actor projects and potential end-users to support their effective and efficient interaction with the 'EU FarmBook'

1.3. Methodology

A methodology for Task 5.1 is outlined in the EUREKA Grant Agreement. It involves a number of steps, beginning with the finalisation of Deliverable 1.6 (*Report on Do's and Don'ts for Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation and Best Practices*) to the generation of a shortlist of the most appropriate/ effective communication and dissemination activities to be used in EUREKA.

In practice, this methodology needed to be adjusted slightly to take into account the delays on the completion of the necessary activities in WP1 and the preparation of D1.6. Once available, D1.6 (notably Section 3.2) contained a list of the most successful communication and dissemination activities identified in the 101 multi-actor projects surveyed in WP1. Deliverable 1.6 does, however, lack information on the selection of the 'best' communication and dissemination techniques, specifically for the needs of EUREKA. The interdependence of tasks and deliverables were not recognised well enough and other foreseen sources (WP2) of information had to be adjusted also.

The identified activities from D1.6 served as the basis for the questions of an online validation survey performed in this task (T5.1). This validation exercise was originally expected to be organised during the macro-regional workshops planned in WP2 (Task 2.1 and review of end-user types). Due to the COVID-19 situation, these workshops were organised in a virtual form, which placed some limitations on the types and richness of the feedback possible from potential end-users in a range of regional and national contexts. The online validation survey was open from 1-15 March 2021, and the invitations to the survey were sent to the EUREKA partners and members of the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP). To identify the most important needs of online repositories and knowledge platforms, the decision was made to reach out to the community of people who were already focusing on the needs of EUREKA. Hence, the EUREKA partners and KIP members were selected due to their level of knowledge and experience with knowledge platforms, and WP5 considered these groups as reasonably and largely representative of the target groups. The survey used a mixed method design with a combination of quantitative and qualitative questions. A total of 53 respondents answered the survey (see Annex 1.2 for detailed information).

For the development of guidelines, analysis of the collected input in Task 1.4 has been performed. The interviewed multi-actor projects were analysed individually through the recorded oral interviews and the written responses to the corresponding questionnaire. This analysis aimed to identify which channels are the most effective for communication and dissemination in a project like EUREKA in order to best leverage from already existing channels and, if needed, implement others. In total, 12 interviews with communication experts of MAPs were analysed (see Annex 2 for more detailed information).

2. Lessons Learned (review of multi-actor projects' C&D activities)

2.1. Communication and dissemination – What is the difference?

One common issue, observed in the majority of MAPs, was a failure to recognise the difference between communication and dissemination (C&D), even among C&D professionals. This common confusion regarding the activities and their purpose can prevent a MAP from reaching the target audience.

The boundaries between activities with regard to communication or dissemination are often blurry and can overlap (Figure 1, source: European Commission). For instance, an article describing the project’s work and achievements, written for communication purposes, could end up in the hands of potential stakeholders outside the project (e.g. researchers) and trigger interest in using the results. Certain tools, channels and activities can serve both C&D purposes, depending on the target group and content.

Figure 1. Understanding Communication and Dissemination (Source: European Commission)

The answers to the T5.1 online survey show overlapping in the list of most effective tools and channels, but the order is slightly different regarding the effectivity for C or D (Figure 2).

In general, what is seen from the analysis of the results from the online survey in T5.1 and the results from T1.4 is that a **website**, which evolves during the project lifetime, following the project results and also the needs of project community, is the most important and used channel for C&D purposes. Also, a better **cooperation** between MAPs is acknowledged. Between MAPs it is acknowledged to make use of already existing media channels (website, newsletters etc.) and build an active community is highly appreciated.

“Communication and dissemination are not only the role of a particular work package. It’s a common work during the whole period of Project. In addition, every partner should work for Project communication and dissemination” – From the FAIRSHARE interview

Figure 2. The respondents were asked to choose the three most effective and useful communication of dissemination tools and channels (n=53).

In addition to the predefined options, general media and national agricultural press, TV channels, agricultural exhibitions, workshops and meetings, newspapers and research articles were mentioned.

Planning of communication and dissemination activities is important not only due to the Horizon 2020 rules and recommendations. The C&D activities should not only be seen as an obligation, but also an important need of a multi-actor approach to share the results. A certain number of communication activities have to be proposed in the beginning of the project. The situations may change rapidly, but series of activities have to be carried out by the project consortium from the beginning.

The involvement of experienced communication specialists in a multi-actor project is strongly recommended to reach optimal communication results and a high impact. The lead partner for communication and dissemination has to manage all external communication activities; act as the central point of contact for all communication activities, monitor and keep record of the C&D activities. While the presence of a specialized agency or team is not always required, it is strongly recommended to include C&D professionals in a project consortium. Else, an agency/team is strongly recommended, as the benefit are most often worth the cost.

Interview of IOF2020: *“Important that communication is handled by true professionals. It is very important because you are building a community, talk with community in a certain way, it’s creates a true feeling of community. Take-away message from my side: Don’t take communication action as a hobby, it should be fully professionally handled.”*

2.2. The target audience

The multi-actor approach is all about bringing people together, with complementary skills from science and practice. Building trustful relationships between organisations and individuals is, therefore, key to success. Different C&D channels can reach different audiences in different countries - and the effectiveness depends on the target group.

The different needs of farmers, advisors, researchers and policy makers is widely recognised:

From the interview with IOF2020: *“Farmers are working all the time; they have no time to be involved in the Project.”*

From the interview with MICOKEY: *“Policy makers have a power to distribute the information they got to the stakeholders and industries. They are also actors who are decision-makers, they can inform industries about new methods.”*

From the T5.1 survey: *“Too often EU jargon or scientific language is used and it is not useful for farming and forestry engagement, we are therefore making our own barriers for successful engagement. I would be interested to engage with farmers and ask them how they would communicate our messages, to bring the understanding of the end user aspect into the communication and dissemination work. We are good at asking the 'what' communication question in relation to channels but not the 'how' in terms of what actually makes sense. This activity should be in the form of workshops not surveys.”*

For efficient stakeholder involvement and for implementing the multi-actor approach into practice, communication has to be kept as simple as possible, minimizing EU jargon and scientific language, e.g. making short, tangible videos and podcasts, with clear messages.

Language skills, and language and information barriers are quite important aspects to take into account. There are substantial differences regarding regional context. In one part of Europe, **language skills and access to information** are not a problem, but in other parts of EU, language is a real barrier in reaching the target groups.

From the interview with DIVERFARMING: *“For farmers we work with common communication strategy developed for each country, because countries and realities are different.”*

From the T5.1 survey: *“Important issue of language - many field agricultural advisors/agricultural practitioners do not speak any foreign language. Google translator is rather not solution for in-depth understanding of more complex message.”*

To improve the uptake of results, reaching a wide range of audiences - spanning from the general public to the core actors helps to spread the information even to the “hard to reach” audiences in their own national language.

The choice between different C&D tools or channels should not be restricted to just one: If the content is interesting and relevant, it should be shared on multiple platforms (adjusted for the relevant target group/s, e.g. with regard to the message, language usage, terminology etc.).

With regard to deliverable D1.6, the best results on social media (concerning the number followers and interactions) have shown that it is recommendable for MAPs to prioritize the use of few channels;

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“The best strategy is to assess the C&D resources that the project has, and choose 2-3 main channels to put those resources into to ensure it's done effectively.”*

Interview with OPTIMA: *“You have to choose your partners to communicate and disseminate. Challenge is to get regularly a good news to present in social media.”*

2.3. Collaboration

One of the most important communication success factors of analysed projects was **collaboration with other multi-actor projects** and existing networks. Collaboration includes sharing through common channels of communication (such as newsletters or social accounts) and the combination of intentions / topics to present the results to the public. Other good examples are organisation of common events, co-written and co-shared posts through the social media and writing of papers with common topics.

Interview with IOF2020: *“It is very necessary to collaborate with other projects: your community is growing, your interactions is more reach. Two similar projects give more synergies. This is win-win situation to all.”*

Interview with NEFERTITI: *“At the planning phase we found many other similar projects. In terms of communication and dissemination of the results it is best strategy, to do it together.”*

The collaboration with other projects and actors is essential in the situation of general **information overload**.

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“To be honest, I would need the information to 'come to me' e.g. via social media, since I am unlikely to make much effort to 'go to it'. Awareness raising messages with links to websites and other outputs are therefore useful.”*

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“People are generally accustomed to using certain channels, so innovation should be disseminated through existing channels, with references to, for example, repositories of knowledge. A particular new site can only be found after hearing about it and knowing the name (it's quite difficult).”*

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“A combination of projects is relevant. So better NOT to communicate about a distinct project and use common platforms as much as possible.”*

Building an active community and involving all actors, especially future end-users is key for long-term sustainability. The potential partners are not only MAPs, also national rural networks, industry clusters, producer organisations (processing cooperatives etc.), professional organisations (farmers' union etc.), national innovation support services, university networks (research alliances), Interreg, Life, ERA-net projects and networks.

As trust and language are always an issue regarding the usefulness of collected or produced knowledge, finding **local advocates, ambassadors and influencers** are an important step for success.

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“Engage and reach relevant ambassador (active on social media or very influent) of each community (farmer, forester, advisor) in each country.”*

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“It seems that advisors and agricultural practitioners in every country, not involved in international projects, usually have their own ways for communication/dissemination etc. Key question - costs related to activities aiming at key target groups operating at national level. Translation, editing, managerial time and resources to reach any target group...”*

According to respondents of the T5.1 survey (Figure 2), a project newsletter is perceived as the least effective C&D tool. The goal of making a dedicated (EUREKA) project newsletter should enhance and increase the input of project partners to produce informative content for end-users, but based on the conclusions from the survey, EUREKA WP5 will increase its focus on leveraging all project partners to share press releases and articles in their own, already existing, organisational newsletters. Promotion of the EUREKA news and guidelines for how to utilise the content/news items of each EUREKA newsletter in the C&D channels of project partners, will be made for each of the upcoming EUREKA newsletters.

2.4. Events

The answers to both the T5.1 online survey and T1.4 interviews shows that various physical and virtual events are effective tools for C&D and exploitation (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Effective collaboration events for EUREKA

Recommended activities are e.g. participation in workshops and meetings at national and EU level, including agricultural shows and exhibitions. Presentations, peer to peer interactions and training help to **build personal contacts and networks over the project lifetime** are recommendable. End-users (farmers and advisors) highly and equally value short visits or exchanges, on-farm demonstrations and training courses on specific topics.

Regarding the EUREKA project, participation in events can bring end-users' attention to the 'EU FarmBook'. Therefore, all listed options are seen as useful, when EUREKA project partners participate in:

- On-farm demonstrations
- Interactive workshops, round-table meetings, group discussions, etc.
- Short visits or exchanges (from a few days up to 2 months) for knowledge exchange and/or training
- Training courses on specific topics
- Joint events with other similar projects
- Virtual meetings
- Conferences and seminars

The project partners of EUREKA should be seen as **multipliers and ambassadors** spreading information about EUREKA results (dissemination) and promoting the use of the 'EU FarmBook' (communication and exploitation).

National events (training workshops) and webinars are an expected activity in EUREKA.

Comment from T5.1 survey: *"Not only the presentation in an event is important, but also the person, who presents."*

According to a majority of interviewees (T1.4) and survey (T5.1) respondents, the most useful events are **physical events**, which enable effective exchange between internal partners (experience exchange) and with stakeholders from diverse application areas. These events should be organised, targeting different audiences to establish a two-way communication and discussion between the project members and the potential end-users of the project results. The consensus, harmonisation, coordination and obtaining common understanding is crucial for building end-user engagement.

Comment from T5.1 survey: *"While virtual meetings may be more accessible, **face to face is essential for real and lasting impact**. People can best learn and connect through real-life experiences involving multiple senses (not only visual and oral)."*

In addition to physical meetings, people are nowadays used to virtual interactions. Online activities have become popular, as farmers are pleased to stay home to be able to solve issues on the farm if needed.

Comment from T5.1 survey: “**Virtual** [meetings and interactions] **bridge distance, let's make clever use of it.**”

Comment from T5.1 survey: “*When face-to-face meetings take place and guests are coming, then the effect is very good due to the establishment of personal relationships. On the other side, many important stakeholders and users of the results will not attend physical meetings. A balance between physical and online meetings is needed.*”

Interview with TOMRES “*Online workshops, as an alternative to physical conferences and meetings. This might be the way, how to reach the people. Connecting online makes it easier to reach more people and increase the number of participants.*”

2.5. Website and knowledge repository

The T5.1 survey shows that the most effective tool/ channel for C&D activities is a project website (Figure 2), which evolves during the project lifetime, following the project results, meeting the needs of project community.

Interview with LIVERUR: “*The **Events Calendar** is one of the most visited pages on our website. It is constantly updated and the content is shared in our social media. So it has a big impact on our stakeholders. The **scientific publications** are ones of the page most visited of our website, also they have been published in other websites (partners, etc) and as papers or articles in scientific magazines.*”

A project website is obligatory according to Horizon 2020 rules.

Comment from T5.1 survey: “*It needs to be considered in the beginning whether a project website is really relevant, or whether to rather focus efforts on other dissemination channels, and then to only make the results available, e.g. in knowledge reservoirs, for as long as possible.*”

A common online knowledge repository can store information after the project has ended. The users are able to display all results, export data and download maps and charts for their own reports and presentations etc.

Interview of IOF2020: “All the solutions worked out by us will be integrated into the Innovation portal created by SmartAgriHubs. This portal promise to be self-sustainable by the end of Project. User community will keep it alive without serious administration. ”

Well-known (EU) knowledge repositories, such as the EIP-AGRI website, are very important not only as places for exchange of knowledge but also as a **common contact point** among potential partners in innovation projects. This helps to avoid the all-too-common situation in which several AKIS actors working in various projects on highly related topics are not aware of each other’s activities and might miss out on important synergies between projects.

Conclusion: A website should be for sharing of projects results, and be targeted the needs of foresters, farmers and advisors (and others), as **urging end-users and project partners to share links ("advertising")** to the EUREKA website from their own organisational websites and Social media channels.

2.6. Social media and videos

The use of social media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn or YouTube) is rapidly growing. The use of different channels varies regarding the age of users, countries etc². Social media posts raise the profile of the project. Via social media channels, projects have an opportunity to reach a high number of relevant stakeholders, and either inform them about the general objectives of the project, to share results from our partners, advertise events and workshops, or to announce open calls.

As EUREKA aims to build the common online knowledge repository, a cooperation between MAPs or other reservoirs is acknowledged: **making use of already existing channels**.

Comment from T5.1 survey: “Not (only) a separate platform but also integration in the communication channels should assure maintenance beyond the project duration.”

Comment from T5.1 survey: “In fact the platform itself should start to build a community and become the farmers’ media channel?”

Results from D1.6 show that the MAPs that achieved the best results in terms of engaging people on social media are those who choose to focus their efforts on **one or two main channels** and on creating specific types of content (e.g. videos for YouTube). This is a more effective and realistic strategy than attempting to be active on all of the popular social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, etc.) at once.

Figure 4. Most effective social media channels by the type of respondent (n= 48)

Interview with DIVERFARMING: “Twitter, Facebook and Instagram and from the beginning we decide a different content for each channel. We are translating our scientific results to Pictures, infographics, short videos and share them. 1770 followers in all social media channels.”

Interview with FAIRSHARE: “On Facebook we are targeting large range of audience. We think that Facebook is not focused in terms of our main target – advisors. On Twitter and LinkedIn you can stay more focused and we achieved good results in targeting.”

The results from the D5.1 survey shows that the most effective social media channel is **Facebook**. This channel was selected by many of the managers (71%) and innovation support specialists (incl. advisors,

² See the material https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

73%). Researchers have found that Facebook is useful to reach farmers. Facebook is widely used for non-professional communication, and information can also reach a wider public.

Interview with DIVERFARMING: “Twitter, Facebook and Instagram and from the beginning we decide a different content for each channel. We are translating our scientific results to Pictures, infographics, short videos and share them. 1770 followers in all social media channels.”

Interview with NEFERTITI: “We implemented special social media strategy. Facebook, Twitter but most of our posts are putted in both places. We choose them because they are most popular social media channels in countries where this Project was implemented. Our goal was to post maximum 2 posts on day. If we organise a meeting, in that case we publish much more posts.”

Twitter is not popular among most farmers, but a lot of policymakers see Twitter as very useful. Twitter is an active channel in multi-actor and H2020 project communities. More than half (59%) of the researchers considered **LinkedIn** to be an effective channel, as they themselves use this channel.

Interview with IOF2020: “Twitter will be the most successful social media channel in our case with the largest number of followers. It seems less people are using Facebook in professional way. In Twitter we can follow policymakers, re-tweet they tweets and initiate interactions. There is no special media channel to farmers, we need to do that in different ways.”

Instagram was seldom mentioned as a useful channel for MAPs, although it is widely used by young generation.

Interview with OPTIMA: “Challenge is to get regularly a good news to present in social media.”

YouTube is exclusively used to share the projects' videos and seldom as a classical social media channel for MAP's. The T5.1 survey indicates that videos are highly appreciated form of C&D (comes in on a fourth place for communication and a second place for dissemination, Figure 2).

Video is a popular tool to show project results and introduce the project partners to build trust among potential users of EU FarmBook. New technologies generate a lot of attraction and allow a fine understanding of the use of farming data for a wide audience.

Interview with SmartAgriHubs: “Virtual reality goggles generate a lot of attraction and allow a fine understanding of the use of farming data for a wide audience.”

Interview with FAIRSHARE: “We are using YouTube as well, short videos have very very good impact. We have almost 1000 followers in YouTube. YouTube was our main social media channel, which allow us to increase stakeholder engagement quickly.”

Interview with IoF2020: “IoF2020 will create a series of stories about the use cases, highlighting the point of the view of the farmers, and these stories will be disseminated on long lasting contents (Streaming video TV channel).”

Figure 5. Conclusions on analysed digital media channels.

Conclusion: As EUREKA aims to build a prototype of a knowledge repository, the target audiences are researchers, MAPs and organisations of advisors, farmers or foresters. It is therefore necessary to take into account that a **social media strategy** is needed in terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project results.

2.7. Newsletters, posters and leaflets

Different materials are important tools for sharing the results, either in digital or printed form. They provide input of possible solutions and efforts from the practical cases for different sectors to be better grasped.

Preparation of press releases, posters, leaflets and articles on the results obtained is seen as an important task. However, when asked about our (EUREKA) project newsletter, in which all partners are invited or directly asked to contribute, many members of the consortium ranked the newsletter as the least appreciated C&D tool (Figure 2). Instead, most considered a poster or leaflet in the beginning of the project, and at least one more when results of the project are available, to be a more useful practice.

The T5.1 online survey revealed that press releases and articles are viewed as effective C&D tools (Figure 2). Press releases and articles are published in different media channels, including specialized science media or farmer magazines. A survey-based study performed in the "parent" or "sister" project of EUREKA (called EURAKNOS) showed that several forms of written materials are expected by the users of online repositories (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Preferred information formats on online repositories (results from the EURAKNOS project)

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“Not all potential users using social media (especially older people). Traditionally such people read national newspapers, watch TV (related programs about farm).”*

Comment from T5.1 survey: *“Despite the fact that digital media have become prevalent, there are people who still prefer newspapers and printed magazines.”*

It is expected that each WP deliver a certain number of **EIP-AGRI practice abstracts** during the project. The requirement of EIP-AGRI practice abstracts is seen as burden for most of MAPs, due in part to their restrictive format.

Interview with TOMRES: *“The only common format for practice abstract was given by Excel sheets. I think it is really difficult, there no ways to include authors/institutions, images or infographics. Excel sheet is terrible for dissemination. Fine for collection, but not for dissemination.”*

3. Guidelines for best communication and dissemination practices for EUREKA

3.1. Recommendations to increase the effectiveness of EUREKA C&D activities, tools and channels

Based on the analysis of T1.4 and the online survey performed in T5.1, we conclude that EUREKA should integrate the following recommendations to increase the effectiveness and impact of the C&D activities.

As mentioned, different tools, channels and activities can serve different purposes depending on the target group and message.

Overall, T5.1 has identified the importance of:

- **Providing messages in different forms** (videos, press releases, infographics and scientific articles) to reach different target groups. Give clear understandable, messages in the project partners' own national language to increase the uptake of information.
- **Building a trusting community** of collaborators and utilising project partners and the community as multipliers/ambassadors.
- **Involving partners** into the general strategy and **providing a clear action plan** to the project partners and **involving C&D professionals** in the project communication and dissemination plan.

Below is a description of how EUREKA and WP5 concretely tackles the recommendations based on deliverable 5.1.

Experienced C&D professionals

- The involvement of experienced communication specialists in a multi-actor project is strongly recommended to reach optimal communication results. This has already been done from the beginning in EUREKA with the involvement of relevant Communications Officers and Communication Consultants as project partners in WP5.

Events

- WP5 organises online (and physical, if possible with regard to the COVID-situation) events to explain and promote EUREKA and the EU FarmBook.
- WP5 will encourage partners to participate in physical events and virtual events etc., so they can spread the word about EU FarmBook possibilities and the benefits from using it.

Website

- WP5 will keep updating the project information displayed on repositories and other media channels (with a preference to those channels that end-users of the project results regularly visit, e.g. websites of farmers' organisations, advisory bodies etc.)

Press releases and articles

- **Regularly provide press releases and articles** of the relevant results on the EUREKA website and C&D channels of project partners. WP5 will make sure that important messages are clear to the target audiences.
- Distribute press releases in social media channels and make it easy for project partners to share it on their already existing channels (see 3.2. How to engage partners in C&D activities).

Newsletter, factsheets, leaflets, brochures

- Collect the **separate articles in EUREKA newsletters** with the highly prioritised messages and news stories to be shared.
- Factsheets and leaflets should be distributed in physical, printed form, at project events and other relevant meetings of project partners.
- Project newsletters should be promoted in already existing channels of project partners to increase the numbers of subscribers; and the news items should be shared in project partners already existing C&D channels such as newsletters, websites and social media channels in national languages (see section 2.2 How to engage project partners in C&D activities).

Videos

- WP5 will produce practical videos that build the trust of potential users of the EU FarmBook to make it easy for the target audiences to understand the benefits from using the EU FarmBook.

Social Media

- WP5 has already developed a **social media strategy and plan (T5.2)** in terms of communication and dissemination of project related information and results throughout the project.
- WP5 will focus on **one or two main channels** and the most relevant news items/social media posts will be distributed in different channels by partners and communities in national languages (see next section).

3.2. How to engage project partners in C&D activities

Based on the results from T5.1, WP5 has identified the importance of utilising already-existing C&D channels and networks of project partners to reach the highest possible number of stakeholders and end-users. Therefore, WP5 has developed a "Communication and Dissemination Guide for the EUREKA partners" on how to share the most relevant news stories from EUREKA in their respective C&D channels. Each of the news items (for websites, newsletters and social media channels) is written in English in the guide, but project partners are urged to translate and share the content in their own national language. The C&D guide is updated on a continuous basis throughout the project, especially with peaks with releases of the EUREKA newsletters. Each partner organisation will at least have one responsible C&D contact person listed in the guide, and they will be contacted by WP5 (AU-ICROFS), when newsletters/articles/press releases and social media posts are published.

The main focus of the initiative of the C&D guideline is, as previously mentioned, to 1) promote the EU FarmBook to increase the number of potential users of the platform and 2) to reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible with relevant information on the results from EUREKA that stakeholders can be learned from in MAPs.

Concretely, WP5 is asking project partners to:

- 1) Insert links on their websites to 1-3 articles or make a translation of these articles to national languages twice per year
- 2) Share posts on their social media channels, translated to national language
- 3) Share news articles in their own newsletters, preferable in national language

See *Annex III First version "C&D Guide for the EUREKA partners"* for the last version of the "Communication and Dissemination Guide for the EUREKA partners".

4. Conclusion

This deliverable provides a shortlist of best communication and dissemination tools and techniques for multi-actor projects like EUREKA to help achieve higher impact. Specifically, Task 5.1 aimed to apply the lessons learned in the multi-actor project community to maximise the impact of the communication and dissemination activities in the EUREKA project, and later in the implementation of the EU FarmBook itself.

The team identified these key issues (Figure 7) as best C&D tools and techniques.

- The involvement of experienced C&D specialists in a multi-actor project is strongly recommended to reach optimal communication and dissemination results.
- The collaboration with other multi-actor projects and the existing networks gives a lot of possibilities regarding common media channels and common events to reduce the feeling of information overload.
- Targeting local advocates, ambassadors and influencers build trust to the messages and help to overcome the issue of native language.
- The most preferred tool/ channel is a project website. A website should be targeted the needs of foresters, farmers and advisors (and others), regarding sharing of project results.
- Various physical and virtual events are perceived as effective for C&D and exploitation. WP5 organises online (and physical, when possible due to the COVID-situation) events to communicate about the project, the results and the EU FarmBook. WP5 will also encourage partners to act as ambassadors and communicate and promote the project and the use of the EU FarmBook at relevant congresses, meetings, seminars etc.
- Factsheets, practical or scientific articles, posters and leaflets either in digital or printed form reach different target audiences. Clear messages should be easy to share by EUREKA and project partners' existing C&D channels to build the AKIS community.
- Social media posts should be used to raise awareness about a project and the project results. Selecting a few channels and creating specific content is an effective strategy.
- Video is a popular tool to share on social media channels to show project results and build trust and interest of potential users of EU FarmBook.

The deliverable gives input for other tasks of WP5, e.g. for the "Communication and Dissemination Guide for the EUREKA partners".

C & D Best practices for EUREKA

- | | | |
|---|--|--|
| Targeting ambassadors |
| Events to participate |
| YouTube value |

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862790.

EUREKA

Figure 7 - Overview of best C&D practices for the EUREKA project.

Annex I Questionnaire and Responses of Validation Survey

Validation of best communication and dissemination practices for integration into EUREKA

The EUREKA project is working to build and test an open-source online platform (a “knowledge reservoir”) to make the practical results generated by the many EU-funded research and innovation projects in agricultural and forestry as accessible and easy to find as possible. The answers of this short survey will be used to double-check and confirm the most effective and useful communication and dissemination practices, channels and tools for EUREKA to use to reach the potential users of the EUREKA online “knowledge reservoir.” These potential users include people such as you - farmers, foresters, advisers, college / university teachers, students, rural businesses, researchers and many more!

Participation in this is voluntary and we will not collect any identifiable personal data.

Thank you very much in advance for your participation!

EUREKA has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862790

Q.1. Please state your profession and nationality

Category	Response	
Manager	Communication manager Project officer Project coordinator	Project leader Team and Project manager Administration specialist
Researcher	Researcher, Professor Senior Scientist	Agricultural scientist, Research associate
Innovation support	Innovation broker Advisor Innovation consultant	Agronomist Research and innovation coordinator Head of innovation support centre
Other	Software developer IT project manager Employee in research institute	No answer (2) Student

Q.2. Most effective and useful communication tools and channels

To effectively raise awareness of the EUREKA project it is important to know which communication channels are for reaching potential users of our results. Please choose the three most effective communication channels based on your experiences with other projects:

Abbreviation for the figure:	Wording of the option
Website	A project website, which evolves during the project lifetime, following the project results and also the needs of project community
Social Media	Through the Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter etc.);
Existing newsletter	Press releases and articles in project partners' already existing newsletters;
Videos	Video presentations of the project (purpose and relevance);
Poster or leaflet	A poster or leaflet in the beginning of the project and at least one more when results of the project are available;
EUREKA newsletter	Press releases and articles in a dedicated EUREKA newsletter;
N/A	I do not have relevant experience

Tool not selected	Popular options
Website (9 persons)	Existing newsletter 7, Social Media 7
Social media (14)	Project website 12, Existing newsletter 11
Existing newsletter (23)	Website 21, Social media 20, Video 19
Video (25)	Website 22, Press release 21

Q.3 Please write below, if you have any other comments on communication channels and tools, relevant for the EUREKA project (n=20)

Type	Answer
Slow start	Start of communication was a bit slow (still ok compared to other projects),
Information overload	One tip: be very clear in internal communications before communicating externally
	There should be something ready to show, during the communication activities
	To be honest, I would need the information to 'come to me' e.g. via social media, since I am unlikely to make much effort to 'go to it'. Awareness raising messages with links to websites and other outputs are therefore useful.
	Like most people nowadays, I'm quite overloaded with news and information. A lot of the 'spare' time I have for growing new information is while commuting, when I mostly use my phone. That means I normally use electronic platforms.
Different groups use different media	All of them are needed and the effectiveness depends on the target group
	I assume "potential users" are mainly the farmers, foresters and advisors? For this group, I think #1 = Facebook, then maybe #2 (tie) are project website & newsletters (EUREKA and existing), #3 LinkedIn? Different for other groups of potential users (e.g., policy makers, researchers).
	Website is essential, but really it is a place to point to from other media e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn etc. Note different channels reach different audiences in different countries. There is not mention of the press above, especially the national agricultural press and that would be an important medium in certain contexts.
	Articles in the press may also help. Despite the fact that digital media have become prevalent, there are people who still prefer newspapers and printed magazines.
	TV channels (information about EUREKA during farmers' shows); Traditional annual agricultural exhibitions Newspaper
	LinkedIn
Connect with others	National rural networks, industry clusters, producer organisations (processing cooperatives, etc.), professional organisations (Farmers Union, etc.), national EIP-AGRI Innovation support services, university networks (research alliances), other H2020, Interreg, Life, ERA-net projects and networks
	Building an active community and involving all actors, especially future end users is key for long-term sustainability.
Events	Participation in several workshops and meetings at national and EU level.
	Book spaces to talk at agricultural shows and events, but make it simple, don't use EU jargon
Common platform	Not (only) a separate platform but also integration in the communication channels of partners Websites from EUREKA should assure maintenance beyond the project duration.
	Articles / contents in project partners' already existing websites
	EC requires the flag, not the project logo, etc. to be communicated. When a farmer sees a project name/logo, he/she thinks 'they get money, I should do the effort'. For others, only a combination of projects is relevant. So better NOT to communicate about a distinct project and use common platforms as much as possible. In fact EUREKA is the setup of the common platform.
Language is an issue	Language is an issue, it would be good if information could be available in more European languages
	Important issue of language - many field agricultural advisors/agricultural practitioners do not speak any foreign language. Google translator is rather not solution for in-depth understanding of more complex message.

Q.4 Most effective and useful dissemination tools and channels

To effectively disseminate results to potential end-users it is important to prioritize between the best available dissemination channels and tools. Please choose the three most important dissemination channels and techniques based on your experiences with other projects:

Abbreviation	Wording of the option
Website	A project website, which evolves during the project lifetime, sharing the project results, targeted the needs of foresters, farmers and advisors;
Platforms	Sharing of information in different knowledge reservoirs and EIP-AGRI website;
Existing newsletter	Press releases and articles in project partners' already existing media channels e.g. newsletters;
EUREKA news	Press releases and articles in a dedicated EUREKA newsletter
Specialized media	Press releases and articles distributed in specialized science media or farmer magazines;
Poster	A poster or leaflet in the beginning of the project and at least one more when results of the project are available
Videos	Video presentations of the project results;
Factsheets	Publication of factsheets on existing National and EU Web platforms;
N/A	I do not have relevant experience

Tool not selected for D	Popular options	Popular Q2 answer (tools for C)
Website (16 persons)	Partner's channels 13 Video/ Specialised media 10	Social media 16, Website 14
Video (22)	Website 21 Press release 20	Website 22, Partners channels 16 Video 7
Partners channels (24)	Website 22 Video 18	Website 24, Social Media 23 Partners newsletter 12
Specialized media (25)	Project website 18 Existing newsletter 16	Website 25, Social Media 20

Q.5 Please write below, if you have any other comments on dissemination channels and tools, relevant for the EUREKA project

Type	Answer/ comment
Mix of C and D	Relevant for the above questions would also be which target audience is to be reached with the communication. Do I answer this question as a consultant / expert or is primarily the exchange with the target group of practicing farmers meant? Same remarks for questions below.
	See communication channels above
	As for Q3.
	My answer is: I cannot answer, and not "I do not have relevant experience", but the answer "I cannot answer" is not included as an option. The may reason of my answer "I cannot answer" is: I think there is a confusion between communication and dissemination channels in the questionnaire, for example research papers are not mentioned as a dissemination channel
	According to the definition of dissemination, this should be more scientific, more academic, more policy oriented. So should it be confusion between communication and dissemination channels in the questionnaire
Local ambassadors	Engage and reach relevant ambassador (active on social media or very influent) of each community (farmer, forester, advisor), in each country
	It seems that ag advisors and agricultural practitioners in every country, not involved in international projects, usually have their own ways for communication/dissemination etc. Key question - costs related to activities aiming at key target groups operating at national level. Translation, editing, managerial time and resources to reach any target group...
Social media	Also through social media
	Although the use of electronic media is growing, the things you can touch, are more to be remembered
	Social media (own/partners)
Events	Presentations and peer to peer interactions during practical workshops and meetings with farmers, foresters and advisors. Also teach the teacher.
	#1 is missing, in my mind: Workshops & Demonstrations – in person best, and virtual still can be very effective.
	Also use events to disseminate
Existing channels	people are generally accustomed to using certain channels, so innovation should be disseminated through existing channels, with references to, for example, repositories of knowledge. A particular new site can only be found after hearing about it and knowing the name (it's quite difficult).
	I use soc media to highlight interesting insights and the website of EUREKA for our results (for the project officer). But to show the relevance, we should connect to our target group platforms, or create them. Good example: biorefinery cluster.
Website	A EUREKA specific website, sharing the project results, targeted the needs of foresters, farmers and advisors and as many as possible partners websites sharing links ("advertising") to the EUREKA website

Q.6 Collaboration and events

EUREKA surveys have shown that face-to-face interaction continues to be considered as one of the most effective tools for knowledge transfer and two-way communication in projects. Please

choose the three most effective forms of face-to-face interaction based on your experience in other projects:

Abbreviation	Wording of the option
On-farm demos	On-farm demonstrations
Short visits	Short visits / exchanges (from a few days up to 2 months) for knowledge exchange and/or training
Interactive meetings	Interactive workshops, round-table meetings, group discussions etc.
Training courses	Training courses on specific topics
Joint events	Joint events with other similar projects
Virtual meetings	Virtual meetings;
Conferences, seminars	Conferences and seminars
Summer schools	Residential summer schools

Collaboration form not selected	Popular options
On-farm demonstrations (18 persons)	Interactive meetings (10), Short visits (8)
Interactive meetings (20)	On-farm demos (14), Training courses (13)
Short visits (22)	On-farm demos (10), Training courses (9)
Training courses (33)	Interactive meetings (24), Short visits / On-farm demos (22)
Joint events (38)	On-farm demos (27), Short visits (26)
Virtual meetings (39)	On-farm demos (26), Short visits (25)
Conferences and seminars (41)	On-farm demos (30), Short visits (29)
Summer schools (47)	On-farm demos (31), Short visits (30)

Q.7 Please write any relevant comments on the advantages/disadvantages (or barriers) of face-to-face interaction for the communication and dissemination of project results

Type	Answer
Right ambassador	not only the presentation in an event is important, but also the person, who presents.
Building bridges	All forms but supported by follow up communication activities leading to network establishment,
Physical contact	No further comment; face-to-face interaction indeed continues to be very important. I don't (yet) have personal experience, but from what I have heard being involved with the EUREKA project so far, it seems that: Short visits / exchanges, On-farm demos, and Training courses on specific topics are all highly and ~equally valued and seen to be useful by participants.

Different actions	not all potential users using social media (especially older people). Traditionally such people read national newspapers, watch TV (related programs about farm).
	Again depends who our target audience is. I assume farmers or advisors in my above responses.
	Depends on the target group, all are important
Physical + online	When face-to-face meetings take place and guests are coming, then the effect is very good due to the establishment of personal relationships. On the other side, many important stakeholders and users of the results will not attend physical meetings. A balance between physical and online meetings is needed.
	While virtual meetings may be more accessible, face to face is essential for real and lasting impact. People can best learn and connect through real-life experiences involving multiple senses (not only visual and oral).
	Please consider the specific situation of farmers and end-users. I heard from colleagues that online activities became very popular, as farmers are pleased to stay home to be able to solve issues on the farm if needed.
	All these are great, if we are very creative. Virtual bridges distance, let's make clever use of it
	Both the "Interactive workshops, round-table meetings, group discussions etc." and "Joint events with other similar projects" could also be "virtual"
Lack of time	Travel requirements, you won't always get the important people in the room because they don't have time to travel

Q.8 Most effective use of social media channels in EUREKA

The use of social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn or YouTube) is rapidly growing. EUREKA has found that projects achieve the best results engaging people on social media when only focusing on one or two main channels. Therefore we need to identify which social media channels are most effective priority channels for EUREKA to use. Please select your two preferred social media channels for achieving high engagement and knowledge sharing with a project:

Social media not selected	Popular options
Facebook (25)	LinkedIn 15, Youtube 14, Twitter 10
YouTube (27)	Facebook 16, LinkedIn 14, Twitter 10
LinkedIn (28)	Facebook 18, Youtube 15, Twitter 13
Twitter (34)	LinkedIn 19, Facebook 19, Youtube 17

Q.9 Please comment, if you prefer another social media channel, and describe why and for which purpose this other social media channel is preferred (n= 9)

Type	Answer
Different actions	See previous one: social media only as a part of complex activities for network building .
Comparison	Who is meant: Advisors - experts - or the farmers. The answer is not necessary the same ...
	Facebook and local agricultural media for farmers, LinkedIn for researchers
	From our research we found that Twitter is not so popular among farmers for dissemination. If you talk to policymakers we have to use Twitter. Instagram is popular for young people.
	I select Twitter for others in the multi-actor / H2020 project community, Facebook more for end users. But all of these listed can be highly effective, if used well and frequently updated.
	Facebook is preferred by me since I don't use Twitter. But, more generally, Twitter is probably more effective than Facebook.
	Twitter and LinkedIn are my choice. I disagree that we should focus only on one or two channels, because use of SM varies enormously by country and target group. I suspect for farmers it would be most useful to use YouTube with short to medium long videos. I have looked for studies demonstrating this but could find only for the US.
	Twitter is also nice but limited in depth. IFOAM does it well
Other media	There are specific social networks in France for the Farmers. His name is Farmr: https://www.farmr.co/index

Q.10. Finally - if you have any additional comments, ideas, or concerns you would like to share, please write them below (n= 9)

Type	Answer
Relevance	There should be something ready, before C or D
	The success of this initiative will depend on the quality of the information available. This is a fairly obvious statement. However, as yet, I don't think there has been enough discussion about the supply of information generated by projects. Many consortia 'over promise' to win funding, and even propose outputs that are no use to anyone. This practice needs to be stopped.

Target groups	My main summary feedback, mostly expressed already in previous comments: The most effective channel depends on the target group, BUT is not restricted to just one: If the communicated content is interesting and relevant, it will be shared – on multiple platforms! And I fully agree that the best strategy is to assess the C&D resources that the project has, and choose 2-3 main channels to put those resources into to ensure it's done effectively.
	Communication language is so important, we are still not good at writing with the audience in mind. Too often EU jargon or scientific language is used and it is not useful for farming and forestry engagement, we are therefore making our own barriers for successful engagement. I would be interested to engage with farmers and ask them how they would communicate our messages, to bring the understanding the end user aspect into the communication and dissemination work. We are good at asking the 'what' communication question in relation to channels but not the 'how' in terms of what actually makes sense. This activity should be in the form of workshops, not surveys.
	Sort of informal division between well-developed ag services/agricultural practitioners of the Old EU and new EU, partly south of Europe. In one part language skills, access to communication are no problem, in other part of EU real barrier in access to these target groups.
Community building	We have ticked most boxes and have lot of time available. I suggest to focus on a knowledge exchange community, especially of national platform builders like green knowledge platform NL.
Use platforms instead of website	In fact the platform itself should start to build a community and become the farmers' media channel?
	It needs to be considered in the beginning whether a project website is really relevant, or whether to rather focus efforts on other dissemination channels, and then to only make the results available, e.g. in knowledge reservoirs, for as long as possible.
Printed materials	Print publications should not be forgotten.

Annex II Deep analysis of Task 1.4 results

• **Topic "Communication in general"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “We have 2 line. First – more traditional. We want to create a public opinion, change image of agriculture. Try to engage farmers and policy makers more. We used traditional communication tools. We are getting good results.” DIVERFARMING
- Regional principle - „For farmers we work with common communication strategy developed for each country, because countries and realities are different.” DIVERFARMING
- “Our Project comparing to other MAPs is big with budget more than 30 million euros. We structured communication as we move on into the Project. First of all we made ourselves more visible with logo and other infographics. In the beginning we were not ready to communicate with farmers, as we did not have any results. During second phase of the Project – raising the visibility of Project to farmers and farmer communities. Harvesting phase (last one) we need engage here policy makers to show them how our instruments Works in practice.” IOF2020
- “European commission should check how many C and D activities are being done by the partners. If they don’t do, they should not receive the funding from this work package.” OPTIMA
- “Social media – artificial way to communicate with people. Conferences and other physical meetings – communicate with people in person.” OPTIMA

Task 1.4 Survey results

- The main objective is NEFERTITI communication activities to reach a wide range of audiences spanning from the general public to the core actors of farming demonstrations. NEFERTITI
- To reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges. SiEUGreen
- We work in case study regions to work with stakeholders in their own context. RustWatch results will be disseminated to all Europe and we could analyse differences and similarities between 6 regions in Europe about how they work with IPM, communication infrastructures, organisation and collaboration between stakeholders, advice etc. RustWatch
- Digital and non-digital strategy. Different communication channels. FAIRshare

• **Topic "Communication: lessons learned"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “In our case were working only engagement physical seminars for farmers. It is important to keep on balance with speaking to farmers/listening of farmers’ opinion and feedback. In case of farmers webinars and online meetings doesn’t work. Older and experienced farmers do not have any kind of interest in participation.” DIVERFARMING
- “Communication and dissemination are not only role of particular work package. It’s a common work during the whole period of Project. In addition, every partner should work for Project communication and dissemination.” FAIRSHARE
- “Important that communication is handled by true professionals. It is very important because you are building community, talk with community in a certain way, it’s create a true feeling of community. Take-away message from my side: Don’t take communication action as a hobby, it should be fully professionally handled.” IOF2020
- “I would suggest to include in the consortium a professional who are working with communication issues.” MICOKEY

- “I think our bottom-up approach Works very well. The most important aspect will be to have a regional cluster (ears and eyes in each region). It is very easy to keep in touch within the context and with reality of certain regions.” SMARTAGRIHUBS
- “Inner communication. Some partners are not responding in time, because they are very busy. You must remind them time to time.” TOMRES

Task 1.4 Survey results

- Effective exchange between internal partners (experience exchange) and with stakeholder from diverse application areas. MycoKey
- With SmartAgriHubs we have organized, and attended, numerous events. Every time we were able to present our project in an innovative way. Whether it was through ‘Regional Cluster tours’, or with an interactive online game. By bringing innovative communication materials to these events, we were able to make events one of our most successful communication activities. Diverfarming
- Define precisely the target groups and use the appropriate materials to reach them. SiEUGreen
- To coordinate and supervise the 23 organizations in LIVERUR, giving them guidelines for communication and exploitation activities, The Plan identifies all the channels, audiences, information and content to be disseminated by the project. It will align key messages for different 3 audiences, the frequency with which communications will take place, milestones for communications, quality controls and performance indicators, as well as responsibilities for undertaking these activities. The implementation of this plan will optimise stakeholder engagement, building trust in the Project from stakeholders, and emphasizing the potential benefits that LIVERUR can deliver. LIVERUR

• **Topic "Communication: challenges"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “Internal communication that was the biggest challenge that we have. Not all partners are connected with communication WP, so we implemented internal Newsletter to all partners and the barrier (some partners are less informed concerning other activities in other work packages) was really achieved.” FAIRSHARE
- “Second, social media. It always difficult to start. During the consortium meeting we split ourselves to three groups: Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. Mission was during these three days working on certain social media channel with the aim to increase amount of subscribers/followers and amount of engaged persons.” FAIRSHARE
- “How to involve the farmers. Farmers are working all the time, they have no time to be involved in the Project. We worked with partners’ representations (umbrella organisations, CEJA as young farmers’ association).” IOF2020
- “You have to chaise your partners to communicate and disseminate. Many partners (farmers for example) don’t want to lose their time on communication and dissemination even is some budget is planned for that. If all partners investing their time similarly to communication and dissemination, the Project goes very well.” OPTIMA
- “Challenge is to get regularly a good news to present in social media.” OPTIMA
- “Our main challenge is communication with our Chinese partner as Facebook and Twitter are prohibited in China.” SiEUGreen
- “Sometimes it is very difficult to engage one or more stakeholder groups. The Project is very big, over 100 partners. We have more than 200 digital innovation SmartAgriHubs. In terms of challenge it is not easy to activate some certain target groups.” SMARTAGRIHUBS
- “Farmers are in particularly difficult approach. Farmers are very closed group of people. Main challenge was to catch their attention on the activities of the Project. We worked a lot with some

activities, where farmers are very active: for example organic agriculture in social media. We used that channels to enlarge our messages.” BOND

- “We discover that involve policy makers is even more difficult than farmers. They are not interested in the results of the Project. They have another channels where they catch necessary information.” BOND

• **Topic "Communication: Social media"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “We are using 4 different channels. 1 public and 1 private Facebook, then we are using Twitter for more formal publications. And we also have Instagram. In Facebook we created a private group, which purpose was to create community of people who are closely in touch during the whole Project period. We have around 150 members in that FB group. We use that channels for distribution of information about our activities and results (including documents).” BOND
- How much time was spent on social media? „There are 4 people working in communication team. 25% of our working time is connected with social media. I can say it is everyday activity.” BOND
- “We have different profiles in Facebook and Twitter in different languages. We work with farmers. Most of them used their own language and we need to spoke with them in proper language. Most better working account in social media is Spanish, as our communication team are from Spain.” DIVERFARMING
- “Twitter, Facebook and Instagram and from the beginning we decide a different content for each channel. We are translating our scientific results to Pictures, infographics, short videos and share them. 1770 followers in all social media channels.” DIVERFARMING
- “On Facebook we are targeting large range of audience. We think that Facebook is not focused in terms of our main target – advisors. On Twitter and LinkedIn you can stay more focused and we achieved good results in targeting. We are using YouTube as well, short videos have very good impact. We have almost 1000 followers in YouTube. YouTube was our main social media channel, which allow us to increase stakeholder engagement quickly.” FAIRSHARE
- “Twitter will be the most successful social media channel in our case with the largest number of followers. It seems less people are using Facebook in professional way. In Twitter we can follow policymakers, re-tweet they tweets and initiate interactions. There is no special media channel to farmers, we need to do that in different ways.” IOF2020
- “Mainly Twitter. Most of our partners were at Twitter. We contacted end-users throw our partners mainly.” LIVERUR
- „Best one – Facebook. Main reason was easy Access. Everybody can Access our webpage easily.” MICOKEY
- “We implemented special social media strategy. Facebook, Twitter but most of our posts are putted in both places. We choose them because they are most popular social media channels in countries where this Project was implemented. Our goal was to post maximum 2 posts on day. If we organise a meeting, in that case we publish much more posts.” NEFERTITI
- “Every MAP should have at least a Twitter account. Another one: you need to post, a least 1 news every day, you have to be regular in your tweets and publications. People in social media don’t want to follow empty and non-informative account.” OPTIMA
- “We focused mainly of Facebook and Twitter. We put a lot of effort on social media strategy and we have a great improvement. We established 2-3 posts per week on specific dates. We used promotion posts only for our application, that have been worked out in the frame of Project. That application is available for people around the World.” SiEUGreen
- “Twitter is most successful channel, because it covered our target groups.” SMARTAGRIHUBS
- “Most recent tweets were done by Twitter. More people are responding to Twitter account than to Facebook.” TOMRES

• **Communication – Professional specialists**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “I am sure, that communication strategy would work better if we could have professional Communicator in each country. Especially that is very important in period when you prepare your proposal (planning period). Usually the persons who are in charge with communication activities are scientists.” DIVERFARMING
- “We choose consultancy agency based in Netherlands and which works for many years together with Wageningen university. They have expertise and long-term collaboration experience.” IOF2020
- “For production of video, we contracted professionals (communication agency) and as well for creation of our webpage.” LIVERUR
- “It was our mistake, we though that everything can be self-made. We (as a scientists) overestimated our capacity to coordinate communication in our Project.” MICOKEY
- “I think for MAP as this, maybe the European Commission should require as mandatory partner a company that Works with communication.” MICOKEY
- “We use only Designer to make some templates and visual graphics. We have very experienced partner in communication and multimedia materials in the Project.” NEFERTITI
- “We are trained ourselves at university. We have specialists in house. We felt that we rather spent money on the field, because communication issues are covered by ourselves. But other projects rather need communication specialists.” RUSTWATCH
- “We as a company, already have experience in communication strategy so we are communication specialist and we are partner in the Project.” SiEUGreen

• **Topic "Important users group"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “Policy makers have a power to distribute the information they got to the stakeholders and industries. They are also actors who are decision-makers, especially in our case (mycotoxins). They can inform industries about new methods.” MICOKEY
- “Extension service, they are interested to know how they can advise a farmer. Breeders as well, as they are breeding new cultivars.” RUSTWATCH

Task 1.4 Survey results

- The primary goal of the communication and dissemination strategy is to influence the knowledge, attitude and behaviour of the defined target groups towards the digital transformation of the agri-food sector. SMARTAGRIHUBS

• **Topic "Dissemination"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “The main dissemination activity that we have carried out were regional workshops. For that purpose we have invited professional researchers in different agricultural topics.” BOND
- “If we have possibility to share information with other (other than multi-actor projects) similar projects, we do it.” BOND
- “We organise scientific conference in China. In China there was enormous participation by China community. Interaction with China was the main goal of the Project. Dissemination worked very well. Also the level of our scientific publication was very high.” MICOKEY
- “We have many indicators in plan, so we are moving smoothly.” NEFERTITI

- “Multimedia materials which were produced in the frame of Project. Another one is NEFERTITI platform, where we post Events. So in one place we have all Events that we organise.” NEFERTITI
- “We launched Innovation portal one year ago, since that moment we have 510 organisations and more than 1400 users. Portal is really interactive platform with our stakeholders and people inside ecosystem. You can easily find a potential partner in terms of sector, region and topic.” SMARTAGRIHUBS
- “I think our Innovation portal is one of the best dissemination channels that we have. By the end of the Project it will be self-sustainable.” SMARTAGRIHUBS
- “Online workshops, as an alternative to physical conferences and meetings. This might be the way, how to reach the people. Connecting online it more easy reach more people and increase the number of participants.” TOMRES

Task 1.4 Survey results

- To involve farmers and provide a repository of success stories and good practices. BOND
- International Conferences were widely participated and increased the already wide existing networking originated in the previous EU project MycoRed. Stakeholders, Institutions and scientists participated actively to these conferences and could debate of the main issues related to mycotoxins. The training courses led several young scientists and Ph.D. students to achieve lot of information on the main and most scientifically updated activities of the project provided by the main representative scientists of the consortium. MycoKey
- The toolbox store analyses and display all results from the project and stakeholders can login and analyse data, export data and download maps and charts for their reports and presentations etc. The Trainings workshops and CSR workshops because this is where stakeholders meet and work with their own data, discuss and exchange ideas. The consensus, harmonisation, coordination and obtaining common understanding is crucial for building a stakeholder driven Wheat Rust Early Warning System. RustWatch
- The Events Calendar is one of the most visited pages on our website. It is constantly updated and the content is share in our social media. So it has a big impact on our stakeholders. The scientific publications are other of the page most visited of our website, also they have been published in other websites (partners, etc) and as papers or articles in scientific magazines. LIVERUR

• **Topic "Dissemination: Collaboration with EIP-AGRI SP"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “We tried to link our Project with EIP-AGRI immediately at the beginning. We write short articles for EIP-AGRI newsletter and disseminate PAs. It is still on-going process. But when we are talking about potential of EIP-AGRI SP in promotion the Project and results I prefer to choose a maximum rate.” FAIRSHARE
- “We have obligation to create 45 practice abstract and disseminate them throw EIP-AGRI SP webpage.” NEFERTITI
- „EIP-AGRI did not taken up any of our messages, promoting of our Events or publications.” SMARTAGRIHUBS
- „The only common format for practice abstract was given by Excel sheets. I think it is really difficult, there no ways to include authors/institutions, images or infographics. Excel sheet is terrible for dissemination. Fine for collection, but not for dissemination.” TOMRES

• **Topic "Dissemination: Collaboration with other partnerships"**

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “It mandatory to collaborate with other projects. First we need to identify all H2020 that can be linked to FAIRshare. In our case: SmartAgriHubs and IoTconnect. We were present in different Events organised by other projects. In addition we are involved in EUFRAS, as it very import channel to link Horizon2020 projects.” FAIRSHARE
- “It is very necessary to collaborate with other projects: your community is growing, your interactions are more reach. Two similar projects give more synergies. This is win-win situation to all.” IOF2020
- “When the topic is the same, similar Project should communicate with each other and try to cooperate instead of compete.” MICOKEY
- “At the planning phase we found many other similar projects. In terms of communication and dissemination of the results it is best strategy, to do it together.” NEFERTITI
- “We collaborate with other similar Project. We communicate throw social media what they are doing and we do. It is pity that commission pays so much money for similar projects, but they don’t collaborate with each other.” OPTIMA

Task 1.4 Survey results

- Articles. NEFERTITI
- Designing effective and appealing Practice Abstracts. TOMRES
- Exchange also in the training courses. MycoKey
- Joint news articles and webinars, joint events and invitation to each other's initiatives. IoF2020
- Newsletter. SmartAgriHubs
- Sharing of data and tools. RustWatch
- Joint workshops, explaining the objective, results to each other. NoAW
- Common events as conference. Common YouTube channel. NEFERTITI
- Experience exchange with colleagues of the dissemination team of twin project SolAce (how to engage partners, how to design practice abstracts). TOMRES
- Meetings among WP leaders; Joint Conferences; exchange of information of the common activities. MycoKey
- Networking sessions and workshops, joint Events. IoF2020
- Events. SmartAgriHubs
- Crop Diversification cluster. Diverfarming
- Joint stakeholder Events. NoAW
- Participation in Rubizmo conference. LIVERUR

• Topic "Exploitation"

Task 1.4 Interview results

- “To ensure the sustainability of the Project beyond the Project lifetime. Decision was to use both a website, where was created a database of best-practices and stories and promote them via social media channels.” BOND
- “Idea is to give an ownership rights to our other partner and he will continue to Update our website even beyond the project.” BOND
- “All the solutions worked out by us will be integrated into the Innovation portal created by SmartAgriHubs. This portal promise to be self-sustainable by the end of Project. User community will keep it alive without serious administration.” IOF2020
- “We keep information in our webpage and Facebook as long as possible for farmers even when Project is already finished.” MICOKEY

Task 1.4 Survey results

- There is a synergy between the 2 projects and IoF2020 ecosystem, findings and solutions will eventually be incorporated in a smart way in the Innovation Portal created by SAH. Also, IoF2020 will create a series of stories about the use cases, highlighting the point of the view of the farmers, and these stories will be disseminated on long lasting contents (Streaming video TV channel). IoF2020
- Different events and communication and dissemination activities will be held after the end of the project in order to exploit the results and to promote the ITC platform which is being developed during the project. All these activities are proposed in a Dissemination Plan Gantt Chart. LIVERUR
- Link inventory platform with other H2020 projects. FAIRshare

Annex III First version "C&D Guide for the EUREKA partners"³

The Work package 5 have collected a series of messages that partners must help to spread through their channels. Each content is preferable to be reused by translating into the current national language.

WP5 will monthly update this content list and notify the managers indicated in the table 3 by each partner.

The main focus of this initiative, as previously expressed, is to give visibility to the EU FarmBook and make it available to as many stakeholders as possible. The priority is certainly given to the social media, as they are widely used by the population (including farmers) and easier to integrate inside the communication strategies of each partner.

WP 5 is available to create ad hoc content, if expressly requested by the partners.

Shortly, WP5 is asking:

- 1) Project partners insert links on their websites to 1-3 articles or make a translation of these articles for national language before August (in the table we will insert links to, e.g., three relevant articles to be shared on websites – and we should urge partners to make a translation in national language, instead of just linking to the EUREKA website)
- 2) Project partners share posts on their social media channels, translated to national language if relevant (in the table, we will make suggestions for short texts that can be copied and used as posts)
- 3) Project partners share news articles in their own newsletters (in the table, we will suggest 2-3 articles and insert a headline and subheading incl. a link for these articles to be shared in their newsletters)

Project output/ overall content	Channels	Picture	Text	Deadlines
What's EUREKA?	Website		Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)	M1
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	

³ The guideline and tables will be finalised and made available for project partners in the end of April 2021

	Social media		<p>Did you know that much of the #agricultural knowledge generated through EU-funded research & innovation projects never reaches the #farmers who need it most? @EURAKNOS & #H2020EUREKA have been working to build a digital platform that bridges the gap between research & practice</p>	
<p>Transition from EURAKNOS to EUREKA</p>	Website		<p>Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)</p>	M2
	Newsletter		<p>Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)</p>	
	Social media		<p>We have a big brother! #H2020EUREKA builds on the experience gained in the @EURAKNOS project, where #bestpractices from all @Horizon2020 projects with a #Thematic Network approach were gathered in a #knowledge repository.</p>	
<p>D1.1 – Map of multi-actor projects</p>	Website		<p>Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and</p>	M

			upload to your own institutional website)	
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	
	Social media		#H2020EUREKA is developing a MA community supported #opensource e-platform, #FarmBook building on a mapping of the #knowledge demand of relevant users of the knowledge produced in these projects - and by the harvest of #bestpractice from more than 120 MA projects.	
D3.1 – Data selection and data quality assessment	Website		Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)	M
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	
	Social media		Post: (text to be written)	
D5.1 – Short list of ‘best available’ multi-actor C&D techniques	Website		Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)	M
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	

	Social media		We've reviewed the communication & dissemination activities of a broad range of #H2020 #multiactor projects. Lots of clear & consistent lessons to be learned and not surprisingly some hot discussion in #H2020EUREKA about the impactful use of #socialmedia	
D5.8 – Practice Abstracts (First set)	Website		Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)	M
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	
	Social media		Post: (text to be written)	
Persona's and User Journeys	Website		Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)	M
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	
	Social media		Do you know what Andres and Marta need? Our approach to developing #personas & #userjourneys for #H2020EUREKA project to ensure that the #digital platform is created with the specific #needs of #users in mind #uxdesign #farming #forestry	

Consortium meeting	Website		Article (link to EUREKA website; ... if relevant, please translate article to national language and upload to your own institutional website)	M5
	Newsletter		Headline: (to be written) Sub-heading: (to be written)	
	Social media		Post: (text to be written)	

List of Partners Channels

Work Package 5 needs to know which tools could be used for the communication and dissemination of project content, including the results and future information of the web platform. It is obviously important that all partners contribute with at least one communication channel.

Understanding the available channels will allow WP5 to prepare the right messages on the contents that best align with the communication strategies of the partners on their channels.

Each partner is asked to place an X on the channels it can or intends to make available to EUREKA. The reference web address (URL) must be linked to the X (see example of UNITO).

Table 2: List of partners channels

Partner	Website	Newsletter	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn	YouTube	Other
UGent	X	X		X	X		
IDELE							
RAU							
AUA							
NAK	X	X	X		X	X	X
ARC	X	X	X	X		X	
IFOAM							
3APTA							
HCS							
ZLTO							
LAAS							
KIS							
UNITO	X			X	X		
LFG							
AU							
AKI (form. NAIK)							
HSRW							
USC							
AC3A							
UM							
CEJA							

Responsible contact person for C&D sharing

WP5 must know the person in charge for each partner of the EUREKA communication activities. Please fill the table with the right information.

We will use this information to start sharing content and messages prepared to communicate EUREKA through partner channels.

Table 3: Responsible contact person for C&D sharing in each organisation (please fill in organisation, name and email address below).

Partner	First and Family Name	Email
UGent	Tyler Arbour	tyler.arbour@ugent.be
IDELE		
RAU		
AUA		
NAK	Aniko Nagy	nagy.aniko@nak.hu
ARC	Konstantin Mihhejev	konstantin.mihhejev@pmk.agri.ee
IFOAM		
3APTA		
HCS		
ZLTO		
LAAS		
KIS		
UNITO	Andrea Masino	andrea.masino@unito.it
LFG		
AU		
AKI (form. NAIK)		
HSRW		
USC		
AC3A		
UM		
CEJA		

Annex IV References

1. Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. EU IPR Helpdesk, 2020
2. EURAKNOS survey - presented at EURAKNOS final conference on 26th of March 2021. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6sT9Nb5yTr4> (10:45)

